

Supplementary Figure 3: Comparison of Fd-GOGAT and NADH-GOGAT proteins from different organisms. The sizes of the proteins are proportionally represented. The number of amino acids of each polypeptide is indicated in brackets

A) Fd-GOGAT

<i>Populus trichocarpa</i>	(1628)	Eudicotyledons	} Viridiplantae
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	(1615)	Liliopsida	
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	(1630)	Pinidae	
<i>Physcomitrella patens</i>	(1626)	Bryophyta	
<i>Klebsormidium flaccidum</i>	(1641)	Klebsormidiales	
<i>Volvox carteri</i>	(1628)	Chlorophyta	
<i>Guillardia theta</i>	(1593)	Cryptophyta	
<i>Porphyra purpurea</i>	(1538)	Rhodophyta	
<i>Synechocystis sp. PCC 6803</i>	(1556)	Cyanobacteria	

B) NADH-GOGAT

<i>Bombyx mori</i>	(2046)	Metazoa	} Opisthokonta
<i>Laccaria bicolor</i>	(2122)	Fungi	
<i>Populus trichocarpa</i>	(2230)	Eudicotyledons	} Viridiplantae
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	(2167)	Liliopsida	
<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	(2218)	Pinidae	
<i>Physcomitrella patens</i>	(2260)	Bryophyta	
<i>Klebsormidium flaccidum</i>	(2212)	Klebsormidiales	
<i>Volvox carteri</i>	(2295)	Chlorophyta	
<i>Guillardia theta</i>	(2149)	Cryptophyta	
<i>Synechocystis sp. PCC 6803</i>	α subunit (1550) β subunit (494)	Cyanobacteria	
<i>Azospirillum brasilense</i>	α subunit (1515) β subunit (482)	Proteobacteria	